

Effect on Flatworms Foraging Behavior Due to Change in Salinity

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Abstract. Salinity is one of the key environmental factors that constitute the biogeographical boundary of aquatic organisms, and affects the distribution, abundance and behavior of aquatic organisms. However, little is known about the relationship between salinity changes and foraging behavior of aquatic organisms. In this research, I chose the marine flatworms *Paucumara* sp. as my research target to study the influence of salinity changes on the foraging behavior. In salt water with a salinity of 20ppt, the foraging behavior of the flatworms was comparable to the seawater control (30ppt). In salt water with a salinity of 10ppt, the marine flatworms show a small amount of twitching and crouching behavior during foraging, and move slowly comparing to the movement speed in seawater. But eventually they succeeded in finding food. In salt water with a salinity of 5ppt, the marine flatworms have no desire to feed and move slowly in a crouched form. In salt water with a salinity of 1ppt, the flatworms did not move and remained crouched, without any foraging behavior observed. In salt water with a salinity of 10, 5, 1ppt, marine flatworms can feed when being placed near food. Overall, decrease in salinity has a significant effect on the foraging process.

1. Introduction

Flatworms are the relatively simple invertebrates (Phylum Platyhelminthes). They are bilaterally symmetrical (i.e., the right and left sides are similar) and lack specialized respiratory, skeletal, and circulatory systems; No body cavity (coelom) is present. The body is not segmented; Spongy connective tissue (mesenchyme) constitutes the so-called parenchyma and fills the space between organs. The digestive cavity has only one opening for the intake of nutrients and the removal of undigested wastes^[1,2]. Hence, food cannot be processed continuously. They perform respiration through the whole surface of the body, which makes them vulnerable to fluid lost, and hence have to restrict them to environments where dehydration is unlikely. These environments include marine and freshwater, moist terrestrial environments such as dead leaves or between grains of soil, and as parasites within other animals.

Marine flatworms are free living creatures that encounter many changes in salinity, such as rain or rising temperatures. To be more specific, marine flatworms living in mudflat experience many salinity changes due to heavy rain. Their foraging behavior during salinity changes is critical to their survival. However, there is little research on the effect of change in salinity on flatworms. In this study, I prepared water of different salinities to determine their tolerance to low concentrations of salt. I recorded their different foraging responses in different concentrations of salt water in order to summarize their behavior patterns.

2. Materials and Methods

Before the experiment started, 40ppt of saline for serial dilution was prepared. As the salinity of seawater is 30ppt, 20, 10, 5, 1ppt of salt water was chosen as the independent variable for the experiment. The petri dishes were marked with two 4 cm markers to clarify the distance between the flatworms and the food. 30 mL of salt water was poured into a petri dish (Petri dish is in an oil and water free state) by a beaker. A marker was placed with 1 g of evenly homogenous liver mixture and waited 15 minutes for the liver odor to spread through the water. Finally, the flatworms were placed on another marker with a pair of tweezers in order to avoid the addition of excess water during the transfer. Cameras on the iPad (2021 iPad pro) were used to record flatworms feeding, and a light shield was placed around the petri dishes in advance. When flatworms were observed to engage in feeding behavior, such as protrusion of a pharynx, the recording was stopped. The above steps were repeated 5 times, with the seawater group as the control group for 8:36 min. Hence 10 min was set to the maximum time. Using flatworms' foraging behavior in seawater as a standard, if flatworms could not find food after ten minutes, the change in salinity was determined to be affecting their foraging process.

3. Results

3.1. Change In Flatworm's Body Structure

As shown in Figure 1, flatworms soaked in 20ppt saline can clearly see the outline of their body and distinguish the head and eyes (Fig. 1a).

After soaking in 10ppt salt water, the flatworm gradually lost its body outline. Compared with 20ppt salt water, the length of its body was shortened, and its body was compressed, but it could vaguely distinguish its body structure, including its head and eyes (Fig. 1b).

After soaking in 5ppt salt water, the body of the flatworm is in a curved shape, and the outline and structure of the body cannot be clearly recognized. The body is darker and shorter than the 10ppt salt water (Fig. 1c).

After soaking in 1ppt salt water, the body structure of flatworms was deformed, and their bodies were round, dark and black (Fig. 1d).

Figure 1. the structure of flatworms' body.

a. the structure of flatworm's body in 20 ppt; **b.** the structure of flatworm's body in 10 ppt; **c.** the structure of flatworm's body in 5 ppt; **d.** the structure of flatworm's body in 1 ppt.

3.2. Change In Food Foraging Path

As shown in Figure 1, the flatworms' foraging route in 20ppt salt water was straight forward (Fig. 2a), proving that a small reduction in salt concentration did not have a decisive effect on their foraging behavior. Despite a curving behavior during the journey, the flatworms managed to find food in the end, with a time of 2 minutes and 45 seconds. Flatworms foraging time in 10ppt saline was longer than that in the 20ppt control, with four crouching and two twitching behaviors (Fig. 2b).

Although it did not go straight for the food at the end of the process, it still took a relatively short time to find the food, which is 3 minutes and 36 seconds. Compared with the first two concentrations, the foraging behavior of flatworms in 5ppt saline changed substantially (Fig. 2c). The flatworm makes its way all the way around in a huddle rather than moving towards the food, moving in a circle around the starting point and eventually unable to find the food. Flatworms did not move actively in 1ppt salt water but detached from the bottom and float along with the water flow. It did not have the desire to forage during the recording period and curled up and floated near the starting point throughout the whole experiment.

Figure 2. the feeding path of flatworms.

a. feeding path in 20 ppt; **b.** feeding path in 10 ppt; **c.** feeding path in 5 ppt; **d.** feeding path in 1 ppt. Red line/dots for crouching; blue line for twitching, and yellow line for normal path.

4. Discussion

My experiment showed that the marine flatworm has a strong tolerance to low concentrations of salt water and can survive in as low as 1ppt salt water. However, in terms of foraging, the seawater flatworms only had foraging behavior in the brine concentration above 10ppt, and could not successfully foraging in the brine concentration of 5ppt and 1 ppt.

The flatworms were not responding to food and unable to move when they stayed in 1ppt salt water. Flatworms are very sensitive to external pressure. When the water concentration on the outside of an animal cell is higher than that on the inside, water is flowing into the cell, it is easy to cause osmosis, the process of water molecules passing through a semi-permeable membrane from a high-concentration solution to a low-concentration solution. Because flatworms don't have an exoskeleton, water molecules can easily pass through a semi-permeable membrane into their body. In order to maintain a balanced environment, the homeostasis system in the flatworm operate by pumping water out of the body cells through active transport. Hence, to combat the concentration gradient, animal cells need extra energy to support active transport, leaving them with no extra energy to find food. This explains the phenomena that flatworms were unable to forage under low salt concentration, indicating the importance of water salinity to the living of flatworms. My results are consistent with Connora and Newman's report (2001), although flatworms in their study were stressed in an even lower salinity, but the flatworm specimens could tolerate a salt concentration of as low as 0ppt^[3]. This demonstrates that flatworms are highly adaptable to changes in salinity, able to survive at low salinity and retain the ability to eat, although they have lost most of their foraging ability.

References:

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